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Cascade process for direct synthesis of indeno[1,2-*b*]furans and indeno[1,2-*b*]pyrroles from diketene and ninhydrin

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Abstract

Novel and efficient multicomponent reactions (MCRs) involving diketene, ninhydrin (indane-1,2,3-trione) and one primary amine (3CR) or two different primary amines (4CR) were achieved for the successful synthesis of dihydro-4H-indeno[1,2-*b*]furan-3-carboxamides or tetrahydroindeno[1,2-*b*]pyrrole-3-carboxamides, respectively. The merits of this method are highlighted by using either commercially available or easily accessible starting materials, operational simplicity, facile workup procedure, efficient usage of all the reactants, tolerance of a variety of functional groups and ability to conduct under uncatalyzed reaction condition. The products were also isolated by just decantation of the solvent, and for the purification column chromatography was non-required.

Keywords: Dihydro-4H-indeno[1,2-*b*] furan-3-carboxamides, Tetrahydroindeno 1,2-*b*] pyrrole-3-carboxamides, DiketeneNinhydrin (indane-1,2,3-trione), Primary amine